

Project Overview

In the healthcare sector, the generation of waste and the consumption of energy and materials are of serious concern. The transition to a circular economy for such products is crucial for sustainability. A critical step in achieving a product's circular lifecycle is its collection, ensuring that returnable products serve as the basis for subsequent reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing and recycling. In reality, however, many of these products are not returned.

This study explores nudging strategies to improve user abilities in order to promote the voluntary return of digital health products, with a focus on the smart pillbox. It provides redesign recommendations to the smart pillbox, and generates guidelines to be applied to a wider range of smart health-related products.

Reinventing the Smart Pillbox's EoL Return Journey

From User to Returner

Redesign recommendations

Based on user insights and iterative feedback, a number of design recommendations emerged. These included transformative features such as a **'switch for state'**, **printed instructions**, a **'deactivate/reset button'**, an **SMS reminder system** and a dedicated **web/app-based return instruction platform**. These enhancements, visualised in a conceptual example of application, aim to streamline the user's return experience.

Comprehensive Guideline

User Interaction

- Design for 'Returner'
- Key Moments of Nudging
- Seamless Return Reminders
- Change of Perception

Communication

- Lifecycle Communication
- Prominent 'Return' Markings
- Avoid Solely Paper-Based Cues
- Increase Return-Related Elements in Hardware
- SMS Notifications

Trust & privacy

- Provide Data Erasure Methods
- Transparency in Remanufacturing Journey

System

- Digital Integration
- Postal Returns as Primary
- Monetary Incentives

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Improving the return rate of a smart pillbox
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